

Assessment of the capabilities of the MBIR reactor's horizontal experimental channels for neutron therapy*

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of determining the possibility of using the horizontal experimental channels of the MBIR reactor for neutron capture therapy studies. The collimator configuration for the neutron beam extraction with specified properties was justified computationally. The peculiarities of the reactor give grounds for a positive assessment of this prospect, primarily the hard spectrum and the uniquely high intensity of the beams. The paper considers the capability of channel No.5 as the most suitable for neutron capture therapy due to a combination of characteristics. The simplest possible axisymmetric collimator was selected for the calculations to assess the key functionalities of neutron capture therapy. The configuration and material composition of the collimator are defined by the experience of calculations. Two fundamental characteristics were analyzed to assess the capabilities of the neutron beam of MBIR's channel No.5 for neutron capture therapy. These are the dose in the target (soft tumor tissue) containing 65 ppm of ¹⁰B, and the dose in healthy tissue containing 18 ppm of ¹⁰B. The task in the series of calculations was as follows: to determine the dynamics of the key values for neutron capture therapy with a variable thickness of the moderator in the collimator channel – the time for gaining a fixed “therapeutic” dose in the target (tumor) and the time for gaining the maximum “tolerance” dose in healthy tissue when the target moves along the depth of the phantom. The distribution of these characteristics through the depth of the tissue allows us to conclude that the beam extraction configuration under consideration is effective. The obtained results of the spectral neutron distribution at the outlet of channel No.5 and the estimated dose characteristics in healthy tissue and in the tumor confirm that it is technically possible to use this channel for neutron capture therapy.

Keywords

MBIR, neutron capture therapy, horizontal experimental channel, collimator, therapeutic dose, tolerance dose, neutron beam

Introduction

A multipurpose fast neutron research reactor (MBIR) is under construction by Rosatom State Corporation as part of the Second Federal Project “Formation of a Modern Experimental and Test Bench Framework for the Development of Technologies for Two-component Nuclear Power with a Closed Nuclear Fuel Cycle” under the “Integrated Program

for the Evolution of Facilities, Technologies and Scientific Research in the Field of Using Atomic Energy in the Russian Federation” aiming to provide the advanced development of Russian nuclear industry (Kravets et al. 2023).

The decision to build the MBIR nuclear research facility (NRF) was made in late 2007. The MBIR reactor, currently in the process of being built at the NIIAR site in Dimitrovgrad, Ulyanovsk Region, will become the

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Table 1. Characteristics of fast neutron research reactors

Parameter	FBTR (India)	VTR (USA)	CEFR (China)	BOR-60 (Russia)	MBIR (Russia)
Status	Operated at 50% of design power	Pre-design optimization	Conditionally in operation	In operation	Under construction
Fuel	65 MOX fuel assemblies declared	70%U–20%Pu –10%Zr	Currently UO ₂ 45%, conversion to MOX	UO ₂ , Vibro-MOX	Vibro-MOX with 38.8% Pu content
Commissioning year	1985	2026	2010	1969	2028
Power (thermal) design/current, MW	40/20.3	300/–	60/–	60/55	150/–
Neutron flux density (integral/fast neutrons), cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	3.15·10 ¹⁵ /– (at 40 MW power)	– / 4.35·10 ¹⁵	3.7·10 ¹⁵ /–	3.7·10 ¹⁵	5.3·10 ¹⁵ / 3.7·10 ¹⁵
Operating time per year, h	1900 Design value: 4200	Refueling cycle 2400	–	5700	5700
Service life, years	30	50	40	56	50

world's largest fast neutron research reactor with a thermal power of 150 MW. This is 2.5 times as high as the power of the current BOR-60 fast research reactor operated by NIIAR since 1968.

Table 1 presents technical characteristics of fast neutron research reactors as compared with the MBIR NRF.

Compared to current fast neutron research reactors, the MBIR NRF has unique characteristics.

The key advantage of the MBIR NRF is a large number of experimental volumes accommodated within the core and the reactor reflector, which makes it possible to undertake large-scale in-pile tests in the interests of Russian and foreign developers of nuclear systems.

The MBIR NRF also has ex-vessel experimental devices in the form of vertical and horizontal experimental channels. The MBIR NRF includes six horizontal experimental channels (HEC) and seven vertical experimental channels (VEC). Apart from the extensive range of physical experiments planned, biomedical experiments can be undertaken. Figure 1 shows the layout of horizontal experimental channels (HEC).

Neutron flux density at the outlet

Figure 1. MBIR HEC layout.

of channel No. 5

There are six horizontal experimental channels laid out in the MBIR NRF. HECs Nos. 4 and 5 can be used for biomedical research; a comparative analysis of their characteristics shows that the maximum neutron flux density is in HEC No.5. The capabilities of the MBIR NRF for neutron capture therapy (Locher 1936) were assessed for HEC No.5.

The MCNP5 calculation of the integral flux density at the channel outlet during operation at the reactor rated power using ball detectors (MCNP 2003) gives a value of $\sim 4.0 \cdot 10^{10}$ neutron·cm⁻²s⁻¹, which provides ample opportunities for the spectrum modification in the terminal device.

Figure 2 presents the radial section of the reactor core computational model at the middle of the height in the channel plane (obtained by the MCNP5 input file visualizer).

The collimator of HEC 5 is formed by the cylindrical layers of the shielding materials (zirconium hydride) and the ICRP soft tissue (four-component homogeneous biological tissue). The shielding accommodates a collimator in the form of a truncated lead cone filled with a moderator of variable thickness.

Figure 2. Horizontal sectional view of the MBIR core at the height middle. The collimator device for the spectrum modification is shown.

Inclined channel No.5 has a diameter of 30 cm, which is unique for the neutron reactor beams in existence or under design. The paper proposes a specific configuration of the terminal device for neutron extraction; we will further use the commonly accepted term “collimator” (or “filter” in cases when it comes to the spectral distribution of neutrons (gamma radiation). The selection of the terminal device material and configuration is defined by a long-term experience of calculating the performance of beams for reactors of different types and applications.

Background

The concept of neutron capture therapy (NCT) was proposed by G.L. Locher (the Franklin Institute at Pennsylvania) in 1936 (Locher 1936), shortly after the neutron was discovered by D. Chadwick and an abnormally large capture cross-section was determined for the ^{10}B nuclide by M. Goldfaber. NCT is based on a simple and elegant physical principle. A solution containing a pharmaceutical preparation with the stable ^{10}B nuclide is injected into human blood, this preparation being sorbed in cells after some time. The tumor is irradiated then by a flux of epithermal neutrons. The capture of the resulting thermal neutron by the ^{10}B nuclide leads to a nuclear reaction, and a high-energy alpha particle, a ^7Li ion and a gamma quantum (in 94% of cases) are formed.

“In air” characteristics

To compare the quality of NCT neutron beams, criteria have been developed, which can be conditionally divided into primary and secondary criteria. Primary (“in phantom”) criteria are those determined from dosimetric quantities in the irradiated tissue. In practice, more widespread are secondary (“in air”) criteria determined with no irradiated item:

- epithermal neutron flux density $\Phi_{\text{epi}} \geq 1 \cdot 10^9$ neutron $\cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$;
- ratio of the absorbed gamma radiation dose rate to the epithermal neutron flux density $D_{\gamma} / \Phi_{\text{epi}} < (2 - 5) 10^{-11}$ cGy $\cdot \text{cm}^2$;
- ratio of the absorbed fast neutron dose rate ($E > 10$ keV) to the epithermal neutron flux density $D_{\text{fast}} / \Phi_{\text{epi}} < (2 - 5) 10^{-11}$ cGy $\cdot \text{cm}^2$;
- ratio of the axial epithermal neutron current to flux $J_{\text{epi}} / \Phi_{\text{epi}} > 0.7$.

“In phantom” characteristics

The most commonly used primary criteria include (Kurachenko 2013):

- *Advantage Depth (AD)* – in-tissue depth x , at which the dose in the tumor becomes equal to the maximum dose in the tissue: $D_{\text{tumor}}(x) = D_{\text{tissue}}^{\text{max}}$;

- *Advantage Ratio (AR)* – a unidimensional integral in the organ depth, usually along the beam axis:

$$AR = \int_0^{AD} \frac{D_{\text{tumor}}(x)}{D_{\text{tissue}}(x)} dx \quad (1)$$

- dose rate in the tumor at the maximum AD depth: $ADDR = D_{\text{tumor}}(AD)$.

Traditional requirements for NCT beams

Typically, requirements are formulated for the secondary “in air” characteristics as more accessible and easily definable. The epithermal neutron flux density at the beam outlet is assumed to be not less than $1 \cdot 10^9$ neutron $\cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ during an irradiation session of 0.5 to 1.0 h.

Spectral distributions of neutrons at the beam outlet

Estimates for the spectral distribution of neutrons at the terminal device beam outlet in channel No.5 show that this distribution by shape agrees well with the neutron distributions for the TAPIRO (Italian small-size research reactor (Agosteo et al. 2001) and MARS Russian reactor (Kurachenko et al. 2006) beams (see Fig. 3).

A new paradigm for neutron capture therapy

Current realities and computational capabilities, including the possibility for detailed precision simulation of both the subject area geometry and the combination of

Table 2. “In air” characteristics of reactor beams (Kurachenko 2013)

	Neutron flux density (neutron $\cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot 10^9$)	Epithermal, %	Thermal, %	Fast, %
Desired values for NCT	≥ 1	~ 100	$\rightarrow 0$	$\rightarrow 0$
TAPIRO	1.00	74	20	6
MARS	0.87	81	6	13
MBIR’s channel No.5	27.7	93	0.27	6.5

Table 3. “In phantom” characteristics of reactor beams (Kurachenko 2013)

	AR	AD	ADDR
TAPIRO	5.30	9.70	32.60
MARS	5.24	7.85	32.80
MBIR’s channel No.5	5.42	9.87	190.00

Figure 3. Neutron spectra at the NCT (TAPIRO and MARS) reactor channel outlet and the MBIR's channel No. 5 outlet: E – neutron energy, MeV; Φ – neutron flux density, $\text{neutron}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

physical processes involved in radiation transport (e.g., the TENDL (Koning et al. 2017) and JEFF-3.3 (NEA Data Bank GitLab platform 2024) nuclear data libraries), as well as the experience of respective calculations make it possible to proceed to a new NCT paradigm. Traditional requirements were formulated for the capabilities of two thermal reactor beams that existed in the 1950s (Liu et al. 1996; Riley et al. 2003) and suggested prolonged radiation sessions, fractional irradiation, etc. The new paradigm relies on intensive high-energy beams. In this case, the achievable dose in the target will be defined practically only by the resistivity of the sound tissue around the target, as well as by the target depth.

To illustrate the above, we shall consider a possible irradiation scenario using the neutron beam of the MBIR's channel No.5. These results are compared with the calculation results for a similar scenario for two beams (the MARS and TAPIRO reactors).

The point target moves in a uniform cylindrical phantom along its axis from the phantom base to a depth of 10 to 12 cm; the terminal beam extraction device adjoins immediately the phantom surface and provides normal incidence of the unidirectional beam with a uniform radial distribution of neutrons whose spectrum is formed by the terminal device moderator.

The dose in the tumor and tissue is formed in NCT missions as follows:

$$D_{\text{tumor}} = \text{CBE}_{B,\text{tumor}} \cdot D_{B,\text{tumor}} + \text{RBE}_N \cdot D_N + \text{RBE}_0 \cdot D_0 + \text{RBE}_{\text{fast}} \cdot D_{\text{fast}} + \text{RBE}_{\gamma} \cdot D_{\gamma}, \quad D_{\text{tissue}} = \text{CBE}_{B,\text{tissue}} \cdot D_{B,\text{tissue}} + \text{RBE}_N \cdot D_N + \text{RBE}_0 \cdot D_0 + \text{RBE}_{\text{fast}} \cdot D_{\text{fast}} + \text{RBE}_{\gamma} \cdot D_{\gamma}. \quad (2)$$

Here, RBE is the relative biological efficiency of radiation, and CBE is the combined (cumulative) biological efficiency (Kurachenko 2013) of the $^{10}\text{B}(n,\alpha)^7\text{Li}$ reaction, and D is the absorbed dose. Expressions (2) describe the key components of the dose formed by the outgoing beam:

- $D_{B,\text{tumor}}, D_{B,\text{tissue}}$ – absorbed dose as a result of the $^{10}\text{B}(n,\alpha)^7\text{Li}$ reaction in the tumor and tissue respectively; $\text{CBE}_{\text{tissue}} = 1.3$, $\text{CBE}_{\text{tumor}} = 3.8$;
- D_N – absorbed dose as a result of the neutron interaction with nitrogen nuclei (primarily as a result of the $^{14}\text{N}(n,p)^{14}\text{C}$ reaction), $\text{RBE}_N = 3.2$;
- D_0 – absorbed dose due to reactions with escape of charged particles), $\text{RBE}_0 = 3.2$;
- D_{fast} – absorbed dose due to the slowdown of neutrons on hydrogen nuclei; RBE_{fast} ;
- D_{γ} – absorbed dose formed by the beam gamma quanta as well as by the secondary gamma quanta that accompany the neutron transport in the tissue.

This paper calculates and analyses two dose components to evaluate the capabilities of the MBIR reactor neutron beams: the dose in the target (soft tumor tissue) containing 65 ppm of ^{10}B , and the dose in the sound tissue containing 18 ppm of ^{10}B . The boron content in the tumor and in sound tissue has been unified in the calculator community and allows comparing the quality of NCT beams. The distribution of the key functionalities through the tissue depth makes it possible to conclude that the beam extraction configuration under consideration is effective.

As simple axisymmetric collimator as possible was used to evaluate the key NCT functionalities in the calculations by Kurachenko 2013, its configuration and material composition are defined by the calculation experience. The collimator (see Fig. 2), whose axis coincides with the beam axis, is formed by a truncated cone (a funnel made of lead), the larger cone base facing the neutron source, i.e., the channel outlet. The diameter of the larger base is equal to the radius of the neutron extraction channel and adjoins it closely. The cone is filled with a variable thickness moderator (Fluental™ material). The collimator is immersed in the cylindrical shielding (zirconium hydride material) and irradiates the cylindrical phantom (ICRP four-component homogeneous biological tissue) through the smaller base. The smaller base of the cone adjoining the phantom has a fixed diameter (10 cm).

The source at the collimator inlet was formed based on the calculated spectral neutron distribution at the channel outlet from a precision model of the MBIR reactor core (Fig. 2), using “flux-in-ball-detector” estimates at the channel outlet.

The purpose of the calculation series was to determine the dynamics of the key NCT values (the time the fixed “administered” dose is gained in the tumor target and the time the maximum “tolerance” dose is gained in sound tissue as the target moves through the phantom depth). Calculation results with the following values are presented further: “administered” dose $D_{Adm} = 60$ Gy-equ, maximum “tolerance” dose in soft tissue $D_{Tot} = 12.5$ Gy-equ, variable target depth in phantom [0–12 cm]. Similar calculations allow one to select the collimator configuration and update the irradiation scenario.

It follows from Fig. 4 that the exposure required to deliver a dose of 60 Gy-equ with the MBIR’s beam 5 is many times as small as the traditional NCT paradigm beam exposure. These are more comfortable conditions for the patient and personnel. We shall note that the extraction configuration of the MBIR’s beam 5 is successful: a dose of 60 Gy-equ with any tumor localization in an interval of 0 to 12 cm through the phantom depth (Fig. 5); at the same time, no sound tissue is overexposed; the time during which the tolerant dose of 12.5 Gy-equ is gained exceeds the exposure time during which the administered dose is gained, i.e., no tissue is actually overexposed.

The limiting dose potentially deliverable to the tumor is defined by the need to make so that no maximum exposure for sound tissue (12.5 Gy-equ) is exceeded. Under the selected irradiation scenario, the maximum dose in sound tissue is reached at the phantom inlet (~ 25 Gy-equ); tumor irradiation with a larger dose will lead to the sound tissue overexposure at the phantom inlet.

The neutron beam formed in channel No.5 allows therefore, with quite an acceptable exposure time (~ several minutes), delivering a significant dose to the tumor (tens of Gy-equ) at a depth of ~ 12 cm, while no sound tissue around the target is overexposed.

Figure 4. Time required to deliver a dose of 60 Gy-equ.

Figure 5. Resultant quality characteristic of the MBIR’s NCT beam 5.

Conclusions

An outlook has been given on the MBIR reactor’s neutron beam extraction channels to be used for neutron capture therapy. The peculiarities of the reactor, primarily its hard spectrum and the uniquely high beam intensity, give grounds to assess this outlook as positive.

The paper considers the capabilities of channel No.5 as the most suitable channel for NCT as far as its characteristics are cumulatively concerned. It has been shown that the neutron flux density at the channel outlet is equal to $\sim 4 \cdot 10^{10}$ neutron \cdot cm $^{-2}$ \cdot s $^{-1}$. The neutron beam NCT capabilities were evaluated for the MBIR reactor’s channel No.5 by analyzing two fundamental characteristics: the dose in the target (soft tumor tissue) containing 65 ppm of ^{10}B , and the dose in sound tissue containing 18 ppm of ^{10}B . The distribution of these functionalities through the tissue depth allows one to conclude that the beam extraction configuration discussed is effective.

As a result of the study, the best possible configuration of the collimator was obtained for the neutron beam extraction with specified properties.

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